

STRENGTH ANALYSIS USING THE RESULT OF COMPRESSION MOLDING SIMULATION FOR LONG CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

Composite materials like fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) are becoming more widely used in the automotive industry and have been found very effective in reducing vehicle weight. Recently, long carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics are increasingly used for lightweight structural parts with high stiffness, strength and energy absorption performance. Compression molding is considered one of the most efficient manufacturing processes to mass produce FRP parts for automotive applications. Compression molding can form FRP into complex shapes with relatively low manufacturing cost and short process time. However, this often generates an unwanted fiber orientation, uneven distribution of fibers and fillers, weld lines and matrix rich regions. These forming effects strongly affect the mechanical strength. To analyze these complex phenomena, LSTC and JSOL developed new compression molding simulation techniques for long fiber reinforced plastics using a beam-in-adaptive EFG coupling function in LS-DYNA[®]. In this paper, a compression molding simulation for long carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics is introduced and a new component strength analysis method with a beam-in-SPG coupling model using deformed beams calculated in the compression molding simulation is presented.

1 INTRODUCTION

Automotive manufacturers are considering to use long carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics as a material with the high strength for satisfying strict crash safety performance as well as weight reduction for fuel efficiency. Compression molding has been proven to be an efficient manufacturing process to form a complicated shape in a short time [1]. However, currently there are a very limited number of high-accuracy simulation technologies available to predict the long fiber orientation, filling timing and other aspects required for compression molding. Therefore, in January 2017 a new simulation technology for compression molding of long fiber reinforced plastics was developed in LS-DYNA [2].

In the first part of this paper the new simulation technology for compression molding of long fiber reinforced plastics is introduced. The main features of this new technology are fibers modelled by beam elements and matrix modelled by tetrahedral solid elements with the r-adaptive remeshing function based on an Element-Free-Galerkin (EFG) formulation. Relative motion of beams in the solid elements is simulated by coupling momentum along the normal direction of each beam element. This coupling method transfers load from beam to solid and vice-versa; a so-called strong coupling interaction. Solid elements for the matrix are adequately remeshed with an r-adaptive function which enables large deformations and can generate complex shapes.

In the second step an investigation to apply this new simulation technology to Randomly-Oriented Strand (ROS) thermoplastic composites is presented. Simple compression tests using the ROS thermoplastic composites were performed at various high temperatures and macroscopic mechanical properties during compression molding were measured. This new simulation technology has the capability for beam elements to slide along the beam axial direction with some resistive force from the

solid elements. Macroscopic mechanical properties are controlled by both mechanical properties of the fiber and the matrix and the resistive forces against fibers sliding axially in the matrix.

In the third step a compression molding simulation of the ROS thermoplastic composite is performed to form a complex shaped part with one cross-rib geometry and compared to the real component. The simulation can provide valuable information regarding fiber orientations, areas prone to fiber failure, filling timing, weld line locations, maximum pressing force and so on.

In the final step static compression strength analysis with a beam-in-SPG coupling model using deformed beams calculated in a compression molding simulation is presented and compared to test results.

2 INTRODUCTION OF CAPABILITIES USED IN NEW COMPRESSION MOLDING ANALYSIS

Beam and solid elements are coupled by *CONSTRAINED_BEAM_IN_SOLID (CBIS), which has been implemented since LS-DYNA R8 [3]. CBIS constrains both accelerations and velocities between beam and solid elements (constraint based method). CBIS has a coupling option which applies only in the beam normal direction, thereby releasing constraint in the beam axial direction. As an additional function, an axial coupling force function has also been implemented. The beam and solid axial debonding processes can be modelled with a user-subroutine giving the axial shear force based on the slip condition between beam nodes and solid elements.

A 3D Element-Free-Galerkin (EFG) formulation based on a Mesh-free Galerkin Method was implemented in LS-DYNA 970 during 2001-2002. Following that, a 3D adaptive EFG including r-adaptive remeshing capability was developed to simulate extremely large deformation of metals like 3D forging, extrusion, cold forming, metal cutting, friction stir welding, riveting, etc. [4].

In May 2016 the idea was conceived by JSOL Corporation (JSOL) to combine the new axial beam coupling function in CBIS with 3D adaptive EFG to simulate compression molding of long fiber reinforced plastics. In this method CBIS continues to constrain the beam elements to the tetrahedral solid elements even during the re-meshing process. Livermore Software Technology Corporation (LSTC) improved the code to enable the simultaneous using these two functions with the aid of JSOL's testing and feedback. Figure 1 shows the modelling method using the beam-in-solid coupling function. This new function was implemented in LS-DYNA R10 [5].

Figure 1: Long fibers modelled by beam elements and polymer matrix by solid elements

3 SIMPLE COMPRESSION TESTS

3.1 Identification of macroscopic mechanical properties

Simple compression tests were performed to measure macroscopic mechanical properties of Randomly-Oriented Strand (ROS) thermoplastic composite (Flexcarbon[®] from Suncorona Oda Co., Ltd.). The ROS thermoplastic composite comprises many strands in 2D random orientation. Each strand is a chopped piece of unidirectional (UD) prepreg composite tape made up of carbon fiber and thermoplastic epoxy resin with fiber volume fraction (V_f) of 40%. One strand is 25mm long and 12mm wide.

Figure 2 shows a simple compression test using a disc-shaped test specimen of 75mm diameter and 6mm thickness of the ROS thermoplastic composite. The simple compression test was performed at low velocity (0.1 mm/sec) inside a high temperature chamber, at constant temperatures of 125, 150, 175 and 200 degrees Celsius. The melting temperature of the thermoplastic epoxy resin was 100 degrees. A lubricant was applied to the loading surfaces to reduce friction against the test specimen.

Figure 2: Test specimen and compression test machine with high temperature chamber

Figure 3 shows a full-scale model of the test specimen of the ROS thermoplastic composite. Carbon fibers in one strand are modelled by many elastic truss beam elements in a row. The matrix is modelled using tetrahedral solid elements with the elasto-viscous or elasto-plastic material. The simulation model consists of eight layers of 2D randomly oriented strands. The very large number of fibers in the real composite must be represented by a much smaller number of beams in the model, however the beam cross-sectional area is adjusted to ensure 40% V_f .

Figure 3: Test specimen simulation model

Macroscopic mechanical properties during compression molding are controlled by the combination of sub-scale mechanical properties of the carbon fiber and matrix (Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio and viscosity or work hardening) and resistive forces against fibers sliding axially in the matrix. The resistive forces can be defined by a user-subroutine coupling option, and in this case they are defined as a friction model with a constant resistive force in a proprietary user-subroutine developed by JSOL. In the first step realistic mechanical properties of the carbon fiber and the matrix scaled by Vf were applied to the simulation model. Next the resistive force was tuned to match the loading recorded from test.

Figure 4 shows the final shapes of the test and the simulation results from the simple compression at temperature 200 degrees. Figure 5 shows contact forces of the simple compression tests at four different temperatures. The simulation results are in good agreement with the tests.

Figure 4: Final shapes formed by simple compression at temperature 200 degrees

Figure 5: Contact forces at four different temperatures

3.2 Deformation behaviour of strands

Additional simple compression tests were performed to observe the deformation behaviour of strands during the punching process. Figure 6 shows the test specimen where two strands have glass fibers attached along their longitudinal edges. The 6mm thick specimen consisted of three ROS thermoplastic composite sheets with 2mm thickness for each. The three sheets were bonded together in an oven at temperatures higher than the matrix's melting point. The middle layer sheet contained the strands where glass fibers were attached. These glass fibers are easily visible under X-ray so they can be used to observe the deformation behaviour of the strands after loading.

Figure 6: Test specimen with two strands where glass fibers are attached

Figure 7 shows the deformation of two strands in test and simulation. The red lines show initial location and grey lines the final location. Strand-1 lies perpendicular to the matrix flow and its fibers can be seen to separate during the punching process. Strand-2 is aligned with the matrix flow and its fibers are seen to move in the flow direction. The simulation predicts very similar deformation behaviour of the strands to that seen in test.

Figure 7: Deformation behaviour of two strands of the test and the simulation

4 COMPRESSION MOLDING TEST AND SIMULATION TO FORM CROSS-RIBBED COMPONENT

A compression molding test was performed to evaluate this new simulation technology. Figure 8 shows the ROS thermoplastic composite sheet (Flexcarbon[®] from Suncorona Oda Co., Ltd.) and the simulation model used in the compression molding. The sheet is in a square shape, 100mm x 100mm and 8mm thickness. The simulation model is made by the same modelling method as that developed in the simple compression simulation at temperature 200 degrees.

Figure 8: ROS thermoplastic sheet and simulation model

Figure 9 shows the punch and die used in the test and the simulation. The compression molding test was performed by a heat and cool molding method. The ROS thermoplastic composite sheet was heated in an oven until the temperature reaches 200 degrees. The punch and die were also heated to the same temperature. The heated sheet was moved from the oven to the die and formed in several seconds at 200 degrees. Then the formed sheet was solidified by gradually cooling the punch and die to a temperature of 90 degrees over a period of several minutes. The molded sheet was then released from the molding system.

Figure 9: Compression molding to form cross-rib shaped component

Figure 10 shows the final forming shapes from the test and simulation. The total footprint of expanded material is predicted to be the same as seen in test.

Figure 10: Final shapes formed by compression molding

5 MECHANICAL STRENGTH TEST AND SIMULATION

After the compression molding, a mechanical strength test and simulation were performed. Figure 11 shows the static compressive strength test using the component molded from the carbon ROS thermoplastic composite.

Figure 11: Static compression strength test of carbon ROS thermoplastic composite

Figure 12 shows the simulation model of the component using the Beam in SPG coupling method in LS-DYNA [6]. Beam elements were carried over from the previous compression molding simulation. The polymer matrix was modelled using new meshless Smoothed Particle Galerkin (SPG) elements. SPG elements were given elasto-plastic material properties and rupture was simulated by bonding failure between SPG elements, not element deletion [7].

Figure 12: Beam in SPG coupling model

Figure 13 shows the matrix polymer deformation behaviour of the test and the simulation. The mode of deformation predicted by simulation is very similar to the test result.

Figure 13: Failure behaviors of test and simulation

Figure 14 shows beam axial force distribution. Beam failure occurs at stresses exceeding the tensile strength of carbon fibers.

Figure 14: Beam axial force distribution of simulation

Figure 15 shows reaction forces of the test and simulation. The first peak and overall reaction force level are well predicted by the simulation.

Figure 15: Reaction forces of tests and simulation

6 ON-GOING RESEARCH

6.1 Compression molding simulation of large scale component

Figure 16 shows the punch and die shapes used to produce an automotive component with lattice ribs, and simulation results showing forming behaviour of the polymer matrix and fiber model. This part was designed to represent a structural reinforcement often used in automobiles. The new compression molding simulation method was successfully applied to such a large scale component. We plan to perform a real compression molding using the same mold shape. We will measure deformation behaviour and punch reaction force and compare with this simulation result.

Figure 16: Compression molding simulation of large scale component model

6.2 New function to simulate high accuracy matrix failure behaviour in strength analysis

Our next target is to simulate various forms of matrix fracture more precisely. The beam-in-SPG coupling strength model has a coarse SPG element density for efficient calculation cost. However, such a model can't simulate matrix fracture behaviour in sufficient detail. To solve this problem we plan to develop a new adaptive SPG function where adaptive SPG elements are newly created locally in the matrix fracture area. The concept is shown in Figure 17. As a result we hope that the adaptive SPG function will enable various forms of matrix fracture to be simulated with high accuracy.

Figure 17: Matrix fracture behaviour using adaptive SPG

7 CONCLUSION

This new simulation technology has great potential to simulate compression molding of long carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics with high accuracy and provides much valuable data in the analysis results:

- Filling behavior and timing
- Fiber orientation and deformation
- Axial force of fiber
- Stress occurring in matrix
- Identification of weld line locations and matrix rich region
- Distribution of fiber volume fraction (V_f)
- Punch reaction force
- Heat transfer and temperature distribution
- Other measureable values

Strength analysis using the result of compression molding simulation for a long carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic component was performed successfully and deemed to have great potential to predict mechanical strength with high accuracy. Adaptive SPG is planned to be developed for matrix fracture behaviour.

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